

Adipose cell differentiation in explant-derived cell culture

Daniel Cebo*

Institute of Veterinary Physiology, Free University of Berlin, Oertzenweg 19b, 14163 Berlin, Germany

ABSTRACT

Adipose tissue is derived from the embryonic mesenchyme and contains a stroma that can be easily isolated. Preliminary studies have recently identified a putative stem cell population within the adipose stromal compartment. This cell population can differentiate to the osteogenic, adipogenic, myogenic, and chondrogenic lineages. Enzymatic digestion, the commonly used method of adipose-derived stromal cells isolation, is time consuming and expensive, especially when applied to large volumes of tissue. Additionally, mechanical stress during isolation, use of bacterial-derived products and potential contamination with endotoxins and xenoantigens are other disadvantages of this method. In this study, the characteristics of the cells obtained by adipose tissue explant culture were studied. This technique can be used to reproducibly isolate mesenchymal stromal cells from fat tissue obtained by liposuction as well as surgical resection. Explant culture gave higher yield of cells than digestion method after primary culture. Therefore, explant culture can be used as an effective way to isolate adipose-derived stromal cells for tissue engineering and regenerative medicine, especially in cases of limited starting material.

KEYWORDS: adipose tissue, cell culture, adipogenesis, lipid staining

1. INTRODUCTION

Adipose tissue plays a crucial role in the regulation of energy homeostasis, insulin sensitivity, and lipid/carbohydrate metabolism [1]. In mammals, two types

of adipose tissues exist: white adipose tissue and brown adipose tissue. Recently, white adipose tissue is becoming widely used in regenerative medicine/cell therapy applications, and its physiological and pathological importance is increasingly appreciated [2]. White adipose tissue is composed of differentiated adipocytes, stromal mesenchymal progenitors known as adipose mesenchymal stromal cells (MSCs), as well as endothelial vascular cells and infiltrating leukocytes [2]. The commonly used method of isolating MSCs from adipose tissue is enzymatic digestion [3]. Briefly, white adipose tissue is first minced into small pieces and incubated with collagenase for 1 h. Then, the digests are filtered, washed, and centrifuged to separate the floating adipocytes from the pelleted stromal cells. Irrespective of the source of tissue, enzymatic digestion is time consuming and expensive, especially when applied to large volumes of tissue [4]; decreased cell viability due to lytic activity is also a problem with this method [5].

Primary explant culture is another approach to isolate cells from various tissues [6]. A simple small fragment of tissue that adheres to the growth surface will usually give rise to an outgrowth of cells.

In this study, we found that adipose tissue explants from beef cattle could adhere to the culture surface and fibroblast-like cells migrated from the attached tissue after several days of culture. After *in vitro* expansion these cells were successfully induced into adipogenic lineages, which demonstrated their multipotency. Adipogenic medium was supplemented with the following:

3-Isobutyl-1-methylxanthine (IBMX) is a non-specific inhibitor of cAMP and cGMP phosphodiesterases. The increase in cAMP level as a result of

*dcebo78@gmail.com

phosphodiesterase inhibition by IBMX activates PKA leading to decreased proliferation, increased differentiation, and induction of apoptosis [7, 8, 9].

Dexamethasone is an anti-inflammatory glucocorticoid with a range of effects on cell survival, cell signaling and gene expression. It is used to study apoptosis, cell signaling pathways and gene expression [10, 11].

Indomethacin promotes adipogenesis of mesenchymal stem cells through a cyclooxygenase independent mechanism [12].

Insulin is the most important survival signal for adipocytes. Reduced insulin availability leads to adipocyte apoptosis and excess lipomobilization, possibly exaggerated by adipose tissue inflammation [13-17].

Intracytoplasmic lipid accumulation seems to be directly proportional to the extent of differentiation [18]. This relationship has been commonly used as a qualitative marker of adipose conversion after staining with Oil Red O, a dye that is soluble in lipids and suitable for the histochemical staining of neutral fats and cholesteryl esters [19-22]. A fast and simple method was developed to quantitate the extent of adipose conversion by determining the amount of the intracytoplasmically accumulated lipid in Oil Red O-stained adipose cells.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Cell culture supplies and media additives

Dexamethasone, 3-isobutyl-1-methylxanthine, insulin, Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM/F12), DMEM/Ham's nutrient mixture F12, Hanks' balanced salt solution (HBSS), and 100× antibiotic-antimycotic solution were all purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO). Fetal bovine serum was purchased from Atlanta Biologicals (Lawrenceville, GA). Trypsin-EDTA was purchased from Mediatech Inc. (Herndon, VA).

2.2. Animals

Adipose tissue was collected from beef cattle slaughtered at a local abattoir. Subcutaneous adipose tissue was transported to the laboratory in cold HBSS supplemented with 10% antibiotic-antimycotic solution. Transport time was less than 60 min for the tissue collected at the abattoir. Tissues were collected postmortem from animals slaughtered

for food and not for research; therefore, Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee approval was not required.

2.3. Stromal-vascular cell isolation procedure

On return to the laboratory, tissue was transferred into a sterile cell culture hood and briefly rinsed again in fresh sterile growth medium. Tissue was extensively washed with PBS to remove contaminating debris. After removing excess water and weighing, the samples were minced into very small pieces (less than 5 mm) with scissors and placed in tissue culture flasks under sterile conditions. The spacing between adjacent tissues was around 8-10 mm. Then the flask was tipped up on its side, with the cap loosened by 1/4 turn to allow CO₂ atmosphere exchange, and the tissue was let to "dry" at the bottom of the flask for 1-2 hours. The flask was gently laid back down, allowing media to again surround and cover the tissue.

After the explants adhered to the bottom, the flask was gently laid back down, allowing growth medium containing D-MEM (without FCS) to surround and cover the tissue. The flasks were maintained in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂ at 37 °C, and the medium was changed every day. On the day 7, medium was changed to D-MEM with 20% FCS. Medium was changed every second day. On the day 14, medium was changed to D-MEM with 10% FCS. When the cells grew to 80% confluence they were passaged using standard trypsinization techniques.

2.4. Differentiation experiment

For adipogenesis, cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^4 cells/cm² and incubated in D-MEM with 10% FCS for 48 h to enable them to adhere to the plates. The medium was then changed to adipogenic medium containing D-MEM, 10% FCS, 1 mM dexamethasone, 10 mM insulin, 200 mM indomethacin, and 0.5 mM isobutyl-methylxanthine. The medium was replaced every 2 days. After 1 week of induction the induced cells were analyzed by staining with Oil Red O.

2.5. Examination of culture cells (Lipid staining)

The cultured cells were counted and examined by lipid histochemistry using Oil Red O staining. Oil Red O staining is an assay performed to stain induced adipogenic cultures to detect mature

adipocytes. Oil Red O is a lysochrome (fat soluble dye) predominantly used for demonstrating triglycerides in cells.

Fixing adipogenic cultures: The cultures and the medium were gently removed. Cells were washed three times with PBS, followed by fixation with 1 ml of 10% formalin in phosphate buffer for 1 h at room temperature.

Preparing Oil Red O stain: A stock solution was prepared by weighing out 300 mg of Oil Red O powder and adding this to 100 ml of 99% isopropanol. This stock solution is stable for one year from the date it is made. During the last 15 min of formalin fixation, 15 ml Oil Red O stock solution was mixed with 10 ml distilled water in a 50 ml tube. Incubation was done for 10 min at room temperature. This working solution is stable for only 2 h. A piece of filter paper was placed in a funnel above a second 50 ml tube. The Oil Red O working solution was filtered completely through the filter funnel into the second 50 ml tube and was stored at room temperature.

Staining adipogenic cultures for morphology observation (light microscope): After fixation, the cells were washed with sterile double distilled water and subsequently with 60% isopropanol for 2 min and then stained with filtered 0.35% Oil Red O solution in 60% isopropanol for 10 min at room temperature. Finally, the cells were rinsed with distilled water until the rinsed off water was clear and imaged with light microscopy. The lipids appeared red and the nuclei appeared blue.

Dye extraction for colorimetric assay: Cultures were fixed for at least 1 h with 10% formalin in isotonic phosphate buffer, then washed with water, stained for 2 h by complete immersion in a working solution of Oil Red O and exhaustively rinsed with water. Excess water was evaporated by placing the stained cultures at a temperature of about 32 °C. In order to determine the extent of adipose conversion, 1 ml of isopropyl alcohol was added to the stained culture dish, the extracted dye was immediately removed by gentle pipetting and its absorbance monitored spectrophotometrically at 510 nm.

2.6. Triglyceride enzymatic assay

Intracytoplasmic triglyceride accumulation was determined on total cell extracts using a clinical

enzymatic assay kit (no. 470 694, Boehringer Mannheim Diagnostica). Cell cultures were rinsed three times briefly with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). The cells from each flask were scraped, suspended in 0.2 ml of 0.05 M Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1 mM β -mercaptoethanol, pH 7.4, at 5 °C, and disrupted by sonication for 10 s at 40 W. Total cell extracts were vigorously stirred, and 0.02 ml aliquots were added to 1 ml of assay mixture containing 73.6 mM Tris/citrate buffer pH 8.2, 30.6 mM $MgCl_2$, 7.8 mM sodium cholate, 0.19% isotridecanol polyglycol ether, 0.049 mM ATP, 0.29 mM phosphoenol pyruvate, 0.24 mM NADH, 3 U/ml esterase, 4.0 U/ml pyruvate kinase, 0.5 U/ml lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) and 1.3 U/ml glycerol kinase. After mixing, samples were incubated at 25 °C for 10 min and absorbance at 340 nm was measured to calculate triglyceride concentration [23, 24].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fibroblast-like fat cells derived from mature fat tissue offer unique features for biological study of fat cells. First, they are homogeneous and, therefore, the ratio of differentiation is high (over 70-80%). Second, the rate of differentiation is high. The origin of the fibroblast-like fat cells is not entirely clear, but there are two possibilities. It is conceivable that these cells arise through dedifferentiation of mature fat cells, or they arise from stromal-vascular cells in the tissue [25].

Fat tissue fragments attached to the flasks showed some fibroblast-like morphology on days 10-14. On days 15-21 of culture, the cells began to proliferate extensively. These fibroblast-like fat cells proliferated in dense arrangements until they became confluent. After the culture cells had grown to confluence and proliferation was inhibited by cell-to-cell contact, the differentiation medium was added and the differentiation was observed. In fibroblast-like fat cells, the intracytoplasmic small lipid droplets increased in number and grew larger until they became unilocular.

The lipid droplets were positive by Oil Red O staining and in this study, this was taken as an indication of differentiation of the fat cells. The evaluation of cellular differentiation to mature fat cells was easily done by observing the intracytoplasmic contents of lipid droplets with a light microscope

Table 1. Determination of intracytoplasmic triglyceride content of adipocytes. The cells were grown in culture dishes as described in the 'Materials and Methods'. Two days after confluence, adipose conversion was stimulated with adipogenic medium. Duplicate cultures were fixed and stained with Oil Red O, or used for enzymatic assay. Values are the average from four experiments ($\pm$ SD).

Day of culture	Triglyceride content (μ g/dish)	Triglyceride content (μ g/dish)
	Oil Red O extraction	Enzymatic assay
0	-	0.912 $\pm$ 0.003
7	250.5 $\pm$ 4.3	286.4 $\pm$ 11.7
10	305.4 $\pm$ 8.4	314.9 $\pm$ 7.8
14	303.0 $\pm$ 6.2	305.4 $\pm$ 9.6

0 = two days after fibroblast-like cells reached confluence; 7, 10, 14 = seven, ten, and fourteen days after adding adipogenic medium containing D-MEM, 10% FCS, 1 mM dexamethasone, 10 mM insulin, 200 mM indomethacin, and 0.5 mM isobutyl methylxanthine, respectively.

and Oil Red O staining, or by chemical assay of the intracellular triglyceride. The ratio of differentiated cells in the entire culture was over 70% on day 30 of culture.

Cultures of mature adipocytes were stained with Oil Red O for various periods of time; the dye was extracted and its optical density was determined at the maximum absorbance peak, 510 nm. The extent of adipose conversion was quantitated by staining the intracytoplasmic lipids and comparing with intracytoplasmic triglyceride. The fibroblast-like fat cells were stimulated to adipose conversion by adipogenic medium as described in section 'Materials and Methods'. When adipose conversion was achieved, cultures were fixed and stained with Oil Red O; parallel cultures were subjected to triglyceride determination by the enzymatic assay.

The results reported here (Table 1) show that no significant differences were found in the triglyceride content as determined by either procedure. It can be concluded that Oil Red O stains triglycerides as well. Therefore, this histological dye can be used to quantitate the triglyceride content from stained cultures of mature adipocytes, since these cells seem to accumulate triglycerides. The method described is accurate and sensitive to determine intracytoplasmic triglyceride content and showed a very close correlation ($r = 0.991$, $P < 0.001$) with enzymatic assays of triglycerides.

In this experiment, variation between duplicate flasks and experiments was not higher than 8% on

samples measured by the enzyme assay. A possible source of variation in the Oil Red O method could be related to losses of intracytoplasmic lipids during fixation of cell cultures.

4. CONCLUSION

We studied a new modified method for culturing *in vitro* adipose cells obtained from explants of beef cattle subcutaneous adipose tissue. During cultivation process fibroblast-like fat cells migrated and proliferated from the fat tissue and after reaching confluence they differentiated into adipose cells under the culture conditions described. The process of differentiation was followed by the increase in triglyceride content in the cells. In conclusion, we obtained multipotent stromal cells from adipose tissue by explant culture, and this method was simple, time saving, and gave a high yield of cells. Therefore, explant culture can be used as an effective way to isolate adipose-derived stromal cells for tissue engineering.

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6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

This paper does not contain any conflict of interest.

7. REFERENCES

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